

Figure 1 - Cleaned phasing results for all 35 strains

We present the three plots generated for each strain's cleaned nPhase phasing predictions, generated from the raw predictions. For each strain, the first plot shows the coverage of each predicted haplotig, the second plot shows the discordance level of each predicted haplotig, and the final plot shows an overview of where the haplotigs are along the genome.

AFP - Coverage

AFP - Phased

ANL - Coverage

ANL - Phased

AQH - Coverage

AQH - Phased

AQT - Coverage

AQT - Phased

ARE - Coverage

ARE - Phased

ASB - Coverage

ASB - Phased

ASC - Coverage

ASC - Phased

ASD - Coverage

ASD - Phased

AVN - Coverage

AVN - Phased

AVQ - Coverage

AVQ - Phased

AVS - Coverage

AVS - Phased

AVT - Coverage

AVT - Phased

BBG - Coverage

BBG - Phased

BDL - Coverage

BDL - Phased

BEM - Coverage

BEM - Phased

BHA - Coverage

BHA - Phased

BRP - Coverage

BRP - Phased

BSI - Coverage

BSI - Phased

CFC - Coverage

CFC - Phased

CFE - Coverage

CFE - Phased

CFF - Coverage

CFF - Phased

CFG - Coverage

CFG - Phased

CFH - Coverage

CFH - Phased

CFM - Coverage

CFM - Phased

CFN - Coverage

CFN - Phased

CFP - Coverage

CFP - Phased

CGC - Coverage

CGC - Phased

CPB - Coverage

CPB - Phased

YMD1864 - Coverage

YMD1864 - Phased

YMD1870 - Coverage

YMD1870 - Phased

YMD1871 - Coverage

YMD1871 - Phased

YMD1873 - Coverage

YMD1873 - Phased

YMD1950 - Coverage

YMD1950 - Phased

YMD1981 - Coverage

YMD1981 - Phased

YMD4285 - Coverage

YMD4285 - Phased

